

Good things come in fives

Five ways that Base4NFDI supports the development of RDM infrastructure

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Abstract

Research data management (RDM) services are developed to serve the needs of the community they target in order to build efficient and demand-driven interoperable national services. Base4NFDI is a community-driven initiative that aims to establish long-term sustainable RDM services for the NFDI consortia and beyond. The three-phased approach of Base4NFDI¹ means the services can be adjusted on their development continuum and can be shaped by Base4NFDI's overarching framework. This presentation will give a snapshot of five main project progress highlights, and will reflect on opportunities and challenges for the initiative in relation to building research supporting infrastructure.

1: A coherent, quality-assured framework: The Base4NFDI team have identified areas of support to ensure service development activities meet high-quality standards across the service lifecycle. Each Base4NFDI service that makes it through each of the three phases is accompanied from service conception to its ultimate roll-out into a sustainable service and at each phase certain technical criteria should be met such as software evaluation, service design and criteria². In addition, the services all have a common look and feel and are offered a structured set of added-value workflows to become Base4NFDI 'coherent', for example service websites and tracking tools, legal support, accessibility guides, logos.

¹ <https://base4nfdi.de/process/criteria-for-basic-services>

² <https://base4nfdi.de/process/what-is-expected-for-each-phase>

2: Establishment of transparent processes: The regular onboarding of services into the Base4NFDI framework is fully streamlined and 8 services are underway, driven by a consortia-driven decision-making process with the support of the Technical Expert Committee. Each step of the evaluation and voting process is transparently recorded and the consortia has the opportunity to give input on its requirement for each service at each phase.

3: Technical support for the services: The Base4NFDI team gives input on general aspects of technical service development. This includes “accessible” services, technical requirements, service catalogue criteria, service design guides, software quality, interoperability, KPIs, and usability. Also encouraging services to align beyond the national border and become “EOSC interoperable” at a technical level.

4: Supporting community uptake: Understanding how a community will use a service is critical. Base4NFDI recognises that RDM services need to be clearly communicated and socialised within the communities they serve and not be developed in a vacuum. Service stewards and section liaison officers can be seen as critical “soft infrastructure” - an essential back-bone to support the take-up of services within the consortia, enabling an agile approach to infrastructure development.

5: Social support for the services: Efforts have to be in place to allow NFDI buy-in. Engagement and outreach efforts are established as an essential component of service development as well as embedding the Base4NFDI services within the wider OneNFDI strategy. The three-phase development process allows for adaptation of the service according to community and consortia needs.

The next phase of Base4NFDI is to initiate the service ramp-up phase. When all of the five above ingredients are combined, Base4NFDI will be a success and will be the common basis for data management within the NFDI and will in turn be a key factor for success in a future NFDI.

Keywords: Open science services, infrastructure, service stewards

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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